

FDO PID Profiles & Attributes

Version 2.1

FDO Forum Proposed Recommendation 17. October 2022

This version: [PR-PIDProfileAttributes-2.1-20221017](#)

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1iirLKoWiG9D2ZZ65RqVk89bCwSYwBVHBxk5gLmeNigl/edit?usp=sharing>

Previous version: [PR-PIDProfileAttributes-2.0-20220608](#)

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1c2mZziq5pPmLxMHLcYqIWriYsc2ezGMXvp0E46iljo/edit#>

Editors:

Maggie Hellström, Sharif Islam, Peter Wittenburg

Authors:

Ivonne Anders, Maggie Hellström, Sharif Islam, Thomas Jejkal, Larry Lannom, Ulrich Schwardmann, Peter Wittenburg

Abstract

The FDO Forum needs a comprehensive definition of what a FAIR Digital Object (FDO) is and what its relevant components are. The PID Profiles and the set of kernel attributes that can be used in PID Profiles are such key pillars. The purpose of this paper is to specify these two aspects in order to incorporate them in the comprehensive FDO specification paper to be written.

Status of this document

This document is a Proposed Recommendation 2.1 version, since earlier versions have been extensively discussed in the FDO Forum and community and all comments have been resolved.

Formal References

This document requires tight synchronization with the following normative FDO Documents:

- FDO Requirement Specifications: FDO Forum FDO Requirement Specifications Version 1.0: [WD-RequirementSpec-1.0-20220317](#)
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1dDH6cH5gMUUzzNFQhaWVpmaiPaN7LBkt/edit#heading=h.gjdgxs>
- FDO Configuration Types: [WD-ConfigurationTypes-0.1-20220127.docx](#)
- FDO Machine Actionability: [WD-MachineActionDef-1.0-20211108.docx](#)

Acknowledgments

This document is based on a document that has been intensively defined in FDO TSIG and been edited by an editing team. We would like to thank all who contributed to this early work.

Contents

Abstract	1
Status of this document	1
Formal References	2
Acknowledgments	2
Contents	2
1. Conclusions	3
2. Generic Aspects	3
3. RDA Kernel Information Type WG	4
4. FDO Discussion Results	5
4.1 Profiles	5
4.2 Bonino's Suggestion	6
4.3 Kernel Attributes	7
4.4 Scope of PID Attributes	7
4.5 Processes	8
5. FDO Forum Definitions	8
6 Kernel Attributes by RDA KIT WG	9

7 Errata	10
8 The document collection	10
6 Changes from previous versions	11

1. Recommendations

The following recommendations are made:

1. Each PID registration must be associated with a PID Profile and the reference to the profile must be determined by a mandatory attribute in the PID Record.
2. The PID Profile is an FDO and must have a specified and unified structure.
3. The attributes being specified in the PID Profile and instantiated in the PID Records need to be registered and defined in open and recognised registries.
4. The PID attribute set should be limited to properties which are required for quick inspections and immediate processing and contains
 - a. mandatory attributes specified by the FDO Forum
 - b. optional attributes specified by the FDO Forum and
 - c. community defined mandatory and optional attributes specified by communities

2. Generic Aspects

The FDO Framework specifies requirements for FDO compliance in a way that different implementation technologies are possible. Currently, two approaches are being presented: (1) the Digital Object based approach as described by Kahn & Wilensky in 2006¹ and the RDA Data Foundation & Technology WG in 2014² and (2) the Linked Data approach as defined by the Web-mechanisms and suggestions such as Signposting³.

In the domain of Digital Objects, each PID is resolved to a set of attributes that describe some essential properties of the FDO and refers at least to the FDO's bit-sequence encoding, its content and its type. We call these attributes Kernel Attributes⁴ and to make them machine actionable, we require that they are being defined and registered in an open registry. In the case of Handles/DOIs, we speak about PID records that contain these Kernel Attributes and the PID resolution delivers attribute-value pairs (attribute name and value) in a structured form. In the case of Linked Data approach, a URL would be resolved into a structured landing page as suggested, for example, by Signposting. This landing page is an HTML document that has a

¹ https://www.doi.org/topics/2006_05_02_Kahn_Framework.pdf

² <http://hdl.handle.net/11304/5d760a3e-991d-11e5-9bb4-2b0aad496318>

³ <https://signposting.org/>

⁴ RDA Terminology: RDA Kernel Information Types <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00031>

defined structure and elements which are registered in an open registry accepted by the Web-community.

The PID Profile is a structure that specifies the set of kernel attributes that are being used for PID management (i.e., the repository creating and managing FDOs, for example, will register PIDs associated with the FDOs and needs to specify which kind of defined and registered kernel attributes it is using). In the case of Linked Data the repository will have to specify which elements it will use when creating the landing pages. The definition of PID profiles or Linked Data Profiles guarantees that the resolution result of a PID is predictable, i.e., machines know what they will get (machine actionability).

The following diagram illustrates the relationships in the case of Handle/DOI usage. When a PID is registered according to a profile by a repository, for example, the values of the included kernel attributes are entered into the PID record. When a client software is provided with a PID, it sends a request to get the profile to obtain information on the

Kernel Attributes to be expected. Then, checks regarding the registration status of the attributes could be performed. The software then asks to receive the attribute-value pairs, checks for compliance with the profile and then interprets the values.

If URIs and landing pages are used as in the Linked Data approach, the agent would create a landing page according to the Signposting suggestions. As Signposting suggests, all elements being used to create the Landing Page will be defined and registered in open registries (IANA, schema.org, etc.). The client software is provided with a URL it sends a request to in order to obtain the corresponding LP. It then will parse the HTML structure to identify the elements and their values. For each value, it will look up the element definition to enable interpretation.

A slightly deviating suggestion is made by Luiz Bonino (see 4.2).

3. RDA Kernel Information Type WG

When discussing PID Profiles we should first look to what the RDA KIT WG⁵ stated about what they call PID Kernel Information profile:

⁵ (<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/pid-kernel-information-profile-management-wg>)

PID Kernel Information is a set of attributes stored within the PID record, i.e., information stored at a global or local PID registry and accessible by a resolver. The primary purpose of PID Kernel Information is in support of smart machine actionable decisions that can be accomplished through inspection of the PID record alone. PID Kernel Information profiles are registered schemas for interpreting PID KI records. PID records may be created according to specific profiles and checked for conformance against them. In other words, PID KI records are concrete instantiations of profiles, comparable to how we consider objects as instantiations of classes in object-oriented programming.

Where PID Kernel Information profiles essentially consist of *attributes*, PID KI records consist of attributes and their relevant *values* (key value pairs). A few guiding principles were established as well such as: *Every attribute in a profile describes the object directly and does not describe another attribute in the same profile.*

Attribute	Value type	Example value
LOCATION	URL	http://www.example.com/file-xyz
CREATED	DATE	2018-01-01
PART_OF_DATASET	PID	20.1000/100/dataset001
DATASET_CREATED	DATE	2018-01-31

Examples are given to illustrate a PID record based on a profile including the following attributes: location, creation date, concrete dataset, dataset creation time. Also counter examples are given, e.g., the example in the table above shows a PID record invalid according to the aforementioned principle. Instead, two PID records should be created: one for <http://www.example.com/file-xyz> containing properties LOCATION, CREATED and PART_OF_DATASET, and another PID record for PID 20.1000/100/dataset01 containing properties LOCATION and CREATED.

The RDA KIT WG then describes a set of recommended Kernel Information attributes which must or may be included in a PID record (see appendix A). The cardinality in the profile indicates whether attributes are mandatory or optional and whether they can be specified multiple times.

4. FDO Discussion Results

4.1 Profiles

The TSIG June meeting notes state the following about profiles:

When an FDO has correctly been created including the assignment of a PID, i.e., a PID Profile has been specified and is retrievable, a predictable resolution behavior is being offered. In fact, one could see the PID Profile as a schema that specifies exactly what the resolution step would resolve to and how to interpret the record. In the case that the attributes which are specified in a profile have been defined and registered we will get machine actionable results.

Entities which create PID records such as repositories for example, will define their own profiles according to which they create PID records. In many cases, repositories will not only use one profile, but different ones since they may have collections of different quality for example. The question which needs to be addressed is where to find the PID Profile? Two suggestions were made in TSIG discussions: (1) *One suggestion is to reserve the first kernel attribute for the reference to the PID Profile being used.*⁶ (2) *Another suggestion was to use a Profile-Key (like the "0.profile ID" in the Handle system).* The second option is preferable, because in some PID service implementations there is no canonical order of attributes in the PID record.

Furthermore if a profile is valid for all PIDs with a certain prefix the profile could be specified at the prefix level. It is obvious that we need a harmonization to achieve interoperability. Assuming that for example a repository has received a prefix for assigning PIDs to its holding and if a repository includes collections of different types and different requirements for the kernel attributes, the profile cannot be defined on prefix level.

Two other questions to be addressed are (1) whether we specify the structure for the profile specification and (2) whether we recommend special registries to manage them. Indeed, the PID profiles should be structured in a unified way and a detailed specification needs to be worked out. It needs to include the following information

- PID, name and address of the creating authority (organisation managing the repository)
- Name and email address of the responsible person⁷
- Date of PID Profile specification
- Number of kernel attributes used
- for each attribute: Type PID, Format, Cardinality

PID Profiles are part of the administration of a PID Creator as for example a repository and therefore should be stored and managed by the creator. The PID Profile⁸ is itself an FDO and needs to be accessible as an FDO.

⁶ This mechanism is actually recommended by the RDA document.

⁷ The requirements of GDPR need to be respected.

⁸ It needs to be checked by the FDO Forum whether it makes sense to offer a federated profile registry.

4.2 Bonino's Suggestion

Bonino is working on his own view of PID Profiles described at the website "FDO Framework"⁹. Bonino suggests a restricted set of PID Attributes and suggests including all other properties in the metadata record:

- *The object's type;*
- *The object's metadata record(s); and*
- *Reference(s) to the object's location(s)."*

In doing so Bonino wants to ensure resolution predictability. In terms of what is being described in this documents, Bonino's suggestion can be seen as one specific choice of a profile which would be compliant with what is suggested, if he would include the mandatory attributes as will be specified by the FDO Forum such as the location of the profile which needs to be the first attribute in a PID Record. It should be noted that Bonino's suggestion does not reflect on the different possible FDO configuration types as outlined in the document.

4.3 Kernel Attributes

The TSIG June meeting notes state the following about kernel attributes:

1. *It is widely agreed that the PID record should have a limited set of attributes¹⁰. The PID record is the first information a client will receive about an FDO, i.e. the attributes should support quick inspection. Further indirections to access the PID Record information should be avoided where possible.*
2. *On the other hand, the PID record (given FAIR specifications) supports a deterministic processing behaviour which is the crucial advantage, i.e., from this point of view it does not matter how many attributes are included as long as they are properly specified.*
3. *We are faced with the needs of large communities which for example want to indicate versions in their PID record to easily navigate to the last version, for example, to support efficient processing.*
4. *There is an agreement that the FDO Forum should request that only defined and registered attributes are accepted since otherwise communities will use the records for all kinds of aspects which they could also put in their user-defined metadata.*
5. *There also seems to be agreement that we do not expect individual end-users to define the usage of attributes, but trustworthy and responsible actors such as repositories. We could identify 3 classes of attributes:*

⁹ <https://fairdigitalobjectframework.org>, The website is being modified regularly. We refer to the state in October 2029.

¹⁰ The PID database system needs to offer a very fast resolution speed which may require that the database is not overloaded. There are, however, no hard limitations and the resolution speed will also be dependent on the technology being used.

- a) *mandatory attributes such as for example the reference to the PID profile (if this is agreed upon)*¹¹
- b) *an FDO defined set of kernel attributes which are agreed upon and which require a process and of which those who define profiles can make use*
- c) *a community defined set of attributes which also need to be defined and registered but that are defined by specific communities*¹²

6. *It is fully agreed that we need guidance with respect to the usage of PID records and the setup of profiles and that we need processes to define the set of FDO Kernel Attributes.*

4.4 Scope of PID Attributes

As indicated in chapter 2 the RDA KIT WG defined a set of 15 possible attributes and speaks about “must and may be included in a profile”. Yet we cannot speak about the existence of a set of mandatory attributes as requested in 6.a. We can use the Digital Specimen FDO specifications from Biodiversity as an example to demonstrate that user communities come to different conclusions with respect to the set of attributes to be included. They are using the following attributes in their profile: (1) a local identifier (MNHN-IM-2013-53462), (2) a digital object type definition (ODSType1803), (3) some metadata according to an agreed standard, and (4) the thumbnail image of the specimen (if exists) as payload. None of the agreed sets defined by RDA KIT WG is being used in the PIDs for Digital Specimen FDOs and vice versa none of the attributes mentioned for the Digital Specimen FDO is being listed by RDA KIT WG.

This explains why we urgently need to agree on the suggestion made in 6:

1. FDO Forum needs to define a mandatory set of attributes to be used by everyone. This set of attributes should be small.
2. FDO Forum needs to establish a community wide registry where an increasing number of attributes are being defined and thus can be used by everyone in the FDO community.
3. We should not prevent communities using their own attributes, however, we need to request that they are defined and registered by a respected community¹³.

It should be noted that the inclusion of the attributes mentioned in (2) and (3) are optional and would require documentation, training and guidance.

4.5 Processes

The FDO community needs to define a process to tackle the above mentioned three challenges. We urgently need to establish boards which determine what is mandatory, what should be in the

¹¹ This would imply a minimal set of attributes that must be provided.

¹² It is up to the community to specify rules.

¹³ With IANA the web-community has established a community-wide respected registry. However, IANA is focussing on semantics that are widely used in the web-world.

FDO community wide set of known attributes and with respect to (3) check which process is needed to accept community managed registries.

5. FDO Forum Definitions

For the FDO Forum the following definitions can be made:

Definition PID Profile (DO Case):

The PID Profiles are registered schemas that specify the set of Kernel Attributes that will be used during PID management, will be instantiated including their values in the PID record and will be returned as key-value pairs when the PID is being resolved.

Definition LP Profile (LD Case):

The LP Profile specifies the set of Kernel Elements that will be used during the creation of a Landing Page, will be included as elements in the LP including their values and will be returned as part of the LP when the URI is being resolved.

Definition Kernel Attributes

Kernel Attributes (elements) are those attributes (elements) that may be used in the PID records (URI Landing Pages) to guarantee machine actionability. Therefore, Kernel Attributes (elements) need to be defined and registered in open community supported registries.

Note: Kernel Attributes can be defined by the FDO Community some of which will be mandatory.

Note: Kernel Attributes can be defined by usage communities and registered in accepted registries.

6 Kernel Attributes by RDA KIT WG

	Property identifier	Content format	Cardi-nality	Explanation
1	PID	Handle	1..n	Global identifier for the object; external to the PID Kernel Information
2	KernellInformationProfile	Handle	1	Handle to the Kernel Information type profile; serves as pointer to profile in DTR. Address of DTR federation expected to be global (common) knowledge.

3	digitalObjectType	Handle	1	Handle points to type definition in DTR for this type of object. Distinguishing metadata from data objects is a client decision within a particular usage context, which may to some extent rely on the digitalObjectType value provided.
4	digitalObjectLocation	URL	1..n	Pointer to the content object location (pointer to the DO). This may be in addition to a pointer to a human-readable landing page for the object.
5	digitalObjectPolicy	Handle	1	Pointer to a policy object which documents changes to the object or its Kernel Information record, including particularly object access and modification policies. A caller should be able to determine the expected future changes to the object from the policy, which are based on managed processes the object owner maintains.
6	etag	Hex string	1	Checksum of object contents. Checksum format determined via attribute type referenced in a Kernel Information record.
7	dateModified	ISO 8601 Date	0..1	Last date/time of object modification. Mandatory if applicable.
8	dateCreated	ISO 8601 Date	1	Date/time of object creation
9	version	String	0..1	If tracked, a version for the object, which must follow a total order. Mandatory for all objects with at least one predecessor version.
10	wasDerivedFrom	Handle	0..n	PROV-DM : Transformation of an entity into another, an update of an entity resulting in a new one, or the construction of a new entity based on a pre-existing entity.
11	specializationOf	Handle	0..n	PROV-DM : Entity is a specialization of another that shares all aspects of the latter, and additionally presents more specific aspects of the same thing as the latter.
12	wasRevisionOf	Handle	0..n	PROV-DM : A derivation for which the resulting entity is a revised version of some original.
13	hadPrimarySource	Handle	0..n	PROV-DM : A primary source for a topic refers to something produced by some agent with direct experience and knowledge about the topic, at the time of the topic's study, without benefit from hindsight.
14	wasQuotedFrom	Handle	0..n	PROV-DM : Used for the repeat of (some or all of) an entity, such as text or image, by someone who may or may not be its original author.

15	alternateOf	Handle	0..n	PROV-DM : Entities present aspects of the same thing. These aspects may be the same or different, and the alternate entities may or may not overlap in time.
----	-------------	--------	------	--

7 The document collection

The FDO Forum document collection is the primary source for FDO Forum documents. FDO Forum users, especially from outside the forum, should always be directed to the document collection rather than be sent private copies of documents.

The FDO Forum document collection is organized so as to lead readers most naturally to the current versions of all documents in all document classes. A document archive is also maintained so that previous published versions of documents remain available. The archive also contains the “Historical” documents.

8 Changes from previous versions

The version WD0.1 from TSIG has been turned to this WD1.0 version by resolving all comments that have been made in the TSIG discussions. Therefore, it will now be open to the whole FDO Forum members.

Version	Who	Date	Comment
WD1.0	Editors	17.3.2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the document now refers to the updated FDO Requirement Specification Document WD1.0 which includes an argumentation why FDO needs 3 categories of attributes - chapter 1 is now called “Recommendations” - a note has been added about respecting GDPR - a few typos were corrected - a note was added to 4.3 bullet point 1 to explain the recommendation - chapter 7 “Erata” was deleted since it is not used anymore in documents

WD2.0	Editors	7.6.2022	- some language style improvements and typos were corrected
PR 2.0	Editors	7.6.2022	- copying the WD2.0 into PR2.0
PR 2.1	Editors	17.10.2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - adding all authors of the sub-specification documents to the author list - correcting some typos and style improvements -correcting wrong references - removing this note: (called Profile-Key, like 0.profile in the Handle system) - Clarifying this sentence: The PID Profile is an FDO and has a specified and unified structure. - removing this sentence: The FDO Forum will take steps to make appropriate specifications and to work out processes. - removing this sentence: There could be a mechanism such as LD Profile to allow users to see what can be expected.